

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-206-IG-3% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	3%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 206
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 9:41:02 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:20:51 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.782	342521	15.40	32236
2	7.217	760007	34.17	65692
3	7.704	782792	35.20	64657
4	8.354	338722	15.23	26188

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-203-IG-3% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221014
Vial:	8	Acq. Method Set:	3%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 203
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 1:24:39 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/21/2023 3:46:22 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.785	204987	3.37	19751
2	7.165	5775461	95.01	482207
3	7.690	13135	0.22	1649
4	8.316	85513	1.41	6571